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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HRD PROGRAMME AND ITS ROLE IN ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

Dr. J. Vincent Xavier

Asst professor, School of Management studies,
St. Joseph's College (Autonomous)
Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract

Organizational effectiveness is the concept of how effective an organization is in achieving the outcomes the organization intends to produce. Organizational effectiveness groups in organizations directly concern themselves with several key areas. They are talent management, leadership development, organization design and structure, design of measurements and scorecards, implementation of change and transformation, deploying smart processes and smart technology to manage the firms' human capital and the formulation of the broader Human Resources agenda. If an organization has practices the effective HRD programme, it reflects the effectiveness of the organisation. The LPG policy creates wider opportunities and verities of products to the customers. Customers always willing to prefer their products by various reasons; an organisational viability is closely linked with the timely execution and effective implementation of HRD programmes. Human resource development is a series of organised activities, conducted within a specialised time and designed to produce behavioural changes. In this context the author tries to explore the role of HRD programme in determining the effectiveness of the organisation of the paper production industry, situated in Tamil Nadu, India. It is purely an empirical study. It is a descriptive type of study. Censes method was adopted to collect the data. Data were collected directly through the structured, self-prepared questionnaire. It was properly tested with reliability and validity. The simple percentage analysis and chi square test was applied to analyze the data. The major finding of this study was an effective HRD programmes are played a key role in the organisational effectiveness. This study has some suggestions based on the findings.

Key words: Organisation effectiveness, Human resource development, Oil and Natural Gas Corporation, Tamil Nadu Newsprint and Papers Limited

INTRODUCTION

World is always competitive in nature, most of the decision made by the people based on competition. people have selected their goods and services based on the quality. In India, after introducing of the LPG policy everything has been talked only with a comparative mind and it is linked with its quality. The quality of the particular product or service is based on the company's long range and continuous effort. The quality of the product or service has been assessed based on the proper functioning of the organisation. The regular and committed employees are the valuable assets of the organisation. The effective functioning of the employees is based on the timely and effective implementation of the Human resource development programmes. To achieve the effectiveness of the organisation is possible it's dedicated and service minded employees. They must be provided a better working atmosphere in all the ways. Quality of the development of human resources is essential for any organisation that would like to be dynamic and growth-oriented. Unlike other resources, human resources have rather unlimited potential capabilities. The potential can be used only by creating a climate that can continuously identify, bring to surface, nurture and use the capabilities of people. Human Resources Development (HRD) system is creating such a climate. A number of HRD

techniques have been developed in recent years to perform, every organisation has been developed the HRD program based on its own immediate environment and needs. The current and timely execution of good HRD programmes will help employees to develop their personal and organizational skills, knowledge, and abilities. It includes as employee training, employee career development, performance management and development, coaching, mentoring, succession planning, key employee identification, tuition assistance, and organization development.

Here the researcher tries to explore the role of HRD programmes in an organisational effectiveness.

THE CONCEPT OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

HRD concept was first introduced by Leonard Nadler in 1969 in a conference in US. HRD (Human Resources Development) has been defined by various scholars in various ways. Some of the important definitions of HRD (Human Resources Development) are as follows:

According to Leonard Nadler, (1969) "Human resource development is a series of organised activities, conducted within a specialised time and designed to produce behavioural changes." In the words of Prof. T.V. Rao, "HRD is a process by which the employees of an organisation are helped in a continuous and planned way to:

- ✓ Acquire or sharpen capabilities required to perform various functions associated with their present or expected future roles.
- ✓ Develop their journal capabilities as individual and discover and exploit their own inner potential for their own and /or organisational development purposes.
- ✓ Develop an organisational culture in which superior-subordinate relationship, team work and collaboration among sub-units are strong and contribute to the professional well-being, motivation and pride of employees.

HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

HRD is a process, not merely a set of mechanisms and techniques. The mechanisms and techniques such as performance appraisal, counselling, training, and organization development interventions are used to initiate, facilitate, and promote this process in a continuous way. Because the process has no limit, the mechanisms may need to be examined periodically to see whether they are promoting or hindering the process. Organisations can facilitate this process of development by planning for it, by allocating organisational resources for the purpose, and by exemplifying an HRD philosophy that values human beings and promotes their development.

THE NEED FOR HRD PROGRAMME IN AN ORGANISATION

Organisations can become dynamic and grow only through the efforts and competencies of their human resources. Personnel policies can keep the morale and motivation of employees high, but these efforts are not enough to make the organisation dynamic and take it in new directions. Employee capabilities must continuously be acquired, sharpened, and used. Even an organisation that has reached its limit of growth needs to adapt to the changing environment. No organisation is immune to the need for processes that help to acquire and increase its capabilities for stability and renewal.

HRD FUNCTIONS

The concept of development should cover not only the individual but also other units in the organisation. In addition to developing the individual, attention needs to be given to the development of stronger dyads; dyads are the basic units of working in the organisation. Besides several groups like committees, task groups, etc. also require attention. Development of such groups should be from the point of view of increasing collaboration amongst people working in the organisation, thus making for an effective decision-making. The entire department and the entire organisation also should be covered by development. Their development would involve developing a climate conducive for their

effectiveness, developing self-renewing mechanisms in the organisations so that they are able to adjust and pro-act, and developing relevant processes which contribute to their effectiveness.

Hence, the goals of the HRD systems are to develop:

- ✓ The capabilities of each employee as an individual.
- ✓ The capabilities of each individual in relation to his or her present role.
- ✓ The capabilities of each employee in relation to his or her expected future role(s).
- ✓ The dyadic relationship between each employee and his or her supervisor.
- ✓ The team spirit and functioning in every organisational unit (department, group, etc.).
- ✓ Collaboration among different units of the organisation.
- ✓ The organisation's overall health and self-renewing capabilities which, in turn, increase the enabling capabilities of individuals, dyads, teams, and the entire organisation.

BENEFITS OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

Human resource development now a day is considered as the key to higher productivity, better relations and greater profitability for any organisation. Appropriate HRD provides unlimited benefits to the concerned organisation. Some of the important benefits are:

Human Resource Development makes people more competent. HRD develops new skill, knowledge and attitude of the people in the concern organisations. Through the better HRD programme employees found themselves better equipped with problem-solving capabilities. Employees are assessed on the basis of their performance by having an acceptable performance appraisal system. An environment of trust and respect can be created with the help of human resource development. It improves the all-round growth of the employees. HRD also improves team spirit in the organisation. They become more open in their behaviour. Thus, new values can be generated.

It also helps to create the efficiency culture in the organisation. It leads to greater organisational effectiveness. Resources are properly utilised and goals are achieved in a better way. It improves the participation of worker in the organisation. This improves the role of worker and workers feel a sense of pride and achievement while performing their jobs. It also helps to collect useful and objective data on employees' programmes and policies which further facilitate better human resource planning. Hence, the importance of concept of HRD should be recognised and given a place of eminence, to face the present and future challenges in the organisation.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

The research problem will try to find out whether the effective implementation of Human resource development programme and its role in organization's effectiveness process of the manufacturing industry.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

To know the effective implementation of the HRD programme plays a key role in the organisational effectiveness process.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

There is a significant association between the HRD programme of the organisation and the organisational effectiveness.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study has scope as it covers a wide range of organisational effectiveness strategies viz., Organization mission / vision, Organization culture, Training and development, Team building, and conflict and career and leadership management. This study would not only provide a vital input in the reformulation of organisational effectiveness strategies but also iron out their deficiencies. Further

this study would make the executives understand about the ways and means to develop a sound financial viability and growth. More than this the modified strategies in the light of their perception and views could enhance the performance of the whole organization considerably.

CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK OF OD

Based on the intensive study the researcher, on the experiences he gained through various reviews as well as detailed discussion with the industrial experts of various industries, TNPL and academicians on HRD programmes and organisation's effectiveness he formulated the present frame work. This frame work would resultant that the HRD programme of an organisation is an important factor that guides the employees and the management to proceed in a right way. The identified indicators are follows:

- ✓ Employee welfare
- ✓ Organizational Policy
- ✓ Organizational Culture
- ✓ Overall HRD programmes (Training and development, career planning and management, Leadership development, performance appraisal, counselling)

ORGANIZATION PROFILE

Tamil Nadu Newsprint Paper Limited (TNPL) was established by the Government of Tami Nadu during early eighties to produce Newsprint and Printing & Writing Paper using bagasse, a sugarcane residue, as primary raw material. The Company commenced production in the year 1984 with an initial capacity of 90,000 TPA. Over the years, the production capacity has been increased to 2,45,000 TPA. TNPL exports about 1/5th of its production to of quality papers more than 30 countries around the world.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

For the purpose of the research the researcher has collected various reviews by the previous studies relating with the identified indicators of this study, HRD programmes and organisational effectiveness.

Vijayalakshmi M. & T.V. Rao (2000) have studied the general organizational development practices in India. The conclusion was that, the workforce mobility and diversity are creating new employee needs along with new expectations about the work culture, and these needs. Dell Dennis (2003) has studied the Enhancing Organizational Effectiveness: reinforcing CI as a more reliable tool for HR practitioners and change agents in promoting smooth or seamless change. Larry Hubbell (2004) studied the Struggling with the issue of who the client is in organization development interventions. The author concluded that within a highly politicized and contentious organization, it can be highly problematic for the OD practitioner to work for the organization as a whole. Priscilla Puaah & Subramanian Ananthram (2006) have studied exploring the antecedents and outcomes of Career Development initiatives. The findings revealed that the existence of career development has a direct influence on the achievement of job satisfaction and career commitment. Harry Sminia & Antonie Van Nistelrooij (2006) have conducted a case study on the introduction of Organization Development (OD) techniques in a traditionally top-down lead public sector organization in the Netherlands. The finding of this study on OD inspired bottom-up change approach has a place next to a top-down strategic management change approach.

D. A. Olaniyan and Lucas. B. Ojo (2008) have studied the relative importance of staff training and development in relation to organization effectiveness. This study resulted that, staff training and development is a vital tool for organizational effectiveness. Andrew Santhose (2008) has done a study on evaluating the effectiveness of Training programme at zonal training institute of Indian railways, Trichy, Tamil Nadu. Overall conclusion was that the training programme given to the employee was good. Valerie Garrow (2009) has explored the journey of Organizational Development as a discipline from its roots in the middle of the 20th century to its current status. This research found some close

working relationships between HR, internal OD and external consultants although there can be confusion over roles and responsibilities.

Jacob D (2010) has conducted a research on Organizational Development practices in ONGC, Cauvery Assets, Karaikal. The major outcomes of this research were the new OD models, strategies and interventions have to be adopted in this organization. Levasseur Robert E (2010) has studied the need for a new form of organization development. The authors have concluded that developing a shared vision of a future based on organizational excellence in sustainability, and using collaborative processes that engage, empower, and inspire the participants in the change process.

Raja Abdul Ghafoor Khan, Furqan Ahmed Khan and Muhammad Aslam Khan (2011) had studied the effect of Training and Development. Results shows that Training and Development, has a significant effect on organizational performance and all these have positively affected the organizational performance. Bola Adekola (2011) has explored the link between career planning and career management. This research concluded that, both antecedent variables have an influence on career development. These above studies are more helpful to the researcher to explore the concept further.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

After collected the reviews the researcher had conducted the pilot study in TNPL, Karur, as the universe of the study before the data collection; this study is a Descriptive cum diagnostic method of study. The researcher developed a questionnaire which is framed covering socio - demographic details and the dimensions identified to the HRD practices and organisational effectiveness. The researcher has collected the responses in a manufacturing plant understand and covered all employees to get more authentic result. The universe /population of the study is the executives of the Tamil Nadu Newsprint paper Limited, (TNPL) Karur, in which 6000 direct and indirect employees are working. As this study deals with the executives, all the direct executives numbering 310 are taken for the research. So Census method was applied in this study. In order to achieve the objectives of this research, data were collected both from the primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected from the respondents through a structured questionnaire. The secondary data had been gathered from the sources like books related to organization effectiveness and HRD, previous related research studies, national and international journals and related web journals.

The questionnaire is a self-prepared based on pilot study. The first part of the questionnaire consists of socio economic factors. The Likert scale is used to know the opinion of the executives on five points. The pretest was conducted with 20 respondents to make sure whether the proposed tool, questionnaire was appropriate. The reliability value of the questionnaire is 0.8261; the split half Guttman method and odd and even method of Spearman Brown were used. The correlation, coefficient are used to test the validity. The statistical tools and techniques such as arithmetic mean and simple percentage were used. The hypothesis framed for the study was tested using appropriate tests of significance and the Chi-square test was applied. The limitations of the study is on its face appears to be limited as it is carried out in a single Tamil Nadu government industry, i.e. TNPL. Thus, its findings cannot be generalized to the other industries which are operated on the same line.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The data were analysed both, the percentage and statistical analysis. The first part is analysis of socio-demographic factors.

The table no-01 reveals that the socio-demographic factors of the respondents. From the demographic factors age, gender, educational qualification, designation experiences, and marital status are analysed. Majority of the respondents are in the age group between 41 to 50 years. Most of the respondents in this current study are male. There are only few female respondents. Most of the respondents are professionally qualified. Most of the respondents are with 21 to 25 years of work experience. Only very few number of the respondents are with 16 to 20 years of work experience. Most of the respondents are getting the monthly salary between Rs. 40001 to 50000. Majority of the respondents are married.

Table -1 : Analysis and Interpretation of Data on Socio-demographic factors

S.no	Details	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Age	20-30 = 4.5%	31-40= 3.9%	41-50 =55.8%	51+ = 25.8%	_____	_____
2	Gender	Male- 82.9 %	Female 17.1%	_____	_____	_____	_____
3	Edu Qualification	Diploma 16.8%	BE- 29%	ME 9%	BA, Bsc & B,Com 20.6%	M.A ,M.Sc, M.Com & MBA- 20%	_____
4	Designation	Engineers = 54.8%	Managers (HR& Ad) = 20%	Supervisors - 11.6%	Mark & Sales exe= 10.3%	Others – 3.2%	_____
5	Experience	Up to 5 Yrs- 5.8%	6-10= 11%	11-15= 24.8%	16- 20=5.2%	21-25= 37.1%	26+ 16.1%
6	Monthly income	Up to 30000 =22.6%	30001- 40000= 21%	40001- 50000 44.5%	50001 + 11.9%	_____	_____
7	Marital Status	Married- 87.4%	Unmarried- 12.6%	_____	_____	_____	_____

Source primary data

Interpretation on the effectiveness of HRD program and its role

The table no 02 shows that, the opinion of the respondents on HRD practices and the effectiveness of the organisation. For the purpose of the analysis, there are twenty selected statements analyzed based on the indicators. Majority of the respondents (64.5 per cent) have agreed that the employees are well aware of the organisational policy in all level. Regarding the HRD programmes and how it motivates the employees, 65.6 per cent of the respondents have agreed .The statement regarding any change made in the organisation immediate and well equipped training will be given to the employees to adopt the change, 66.5 per cent of the employees agreed it. Whereas the influence of the training programme it has improved their knowledge, skills and potentiality and the organization motivates the employee to develop themselves in their job position 64.8 per cent of the respondents have agreed. . Most of the respondents (68.4 per cent) have agreed the training evaluation is made properly in the organisation. The next statement regarding the periodical organisational diagnosis in the organisation, most of the respondents (69.5 per cent) have agreed. 60.6 per cent of the respondent have expressed that the organisation has a well-defined roles and authorities. Majority of the respondents (65.5 per cent) have agreed that the HRD programes enhance the quality of the employees. The statement regarding the career development opportunities 61.9 per cent of the employees have accepted that it is good. Regarding the grievance handling method, most of the respondents (65.8 per cent) have agreed that it is good, whereas the relationship between the employees in the organization, 69 per cent of the respondents have agreed. 65.2 per cent respondents have agreed that the facilities provided in the organisation are good. A vast majority of the respondents (82 per cent) have expressed that the performance appraisal system has improved the organisational viability. 57 per cent of the respondent have expressed that the restructuring is made after the diagnosis of the organisation. 54 per cent of the respondents have agreed that good HRIS is maintained in the organisation. Finally regarding the self-discipline between the employees in the organisation, majority of the respondent have (63 per cent) expressed it is good.

FINDINGS

Based On Socio Demographic Factors

In the present study, most of the respondents are engineers. This is comparatively higher than the other groups. This study is conducted in a paper production plant; this industry needs employees who are professionally qualified in handling machineries and equipments, Majority of the respondents are in the age group between 41 to 50 years. On the other hand there are very few numbers in the age group 20 to 30 years. It is observed that there is a vast gap in the recruitment. Most of the respondents in this current study are male .It is observed that TNPL is the manufacturing industry.

There are only few female respondents. Here are the possibility of dealing with hazardous chemicals and poisonous gas. Perhaps the female gender may not prefer this job. Most of the respondents are with 21 to 25 years of work experience. Only very few number of the respondents are with 16 to 20 years of work experience. Most of the respondents are getting the monthly salary between Rs. 40001 to 50000. It is known that employees working in TNPL are getting good salary. Majority of the respondents are married. Remaining is either single or unmarried.

Findings Related To the HRD and the Organisational Effectiveness

Regarding the influence of HRD programmes in the organisational effectiveness, 65.05 percent of the respondents have accepted that the HRD programme is close relation in the organisational effectiveness. It is found that the policy of the organisation is clear (64.5 per cent .It is known the HRD programme motivates the employees (65.6 per cent). Immediate training is given for change made in the organisation (66.5 per cent). The training programme helps to improve their knowledge, skills and potentiality and the organization motivates the employee to develop themselves in their job position (64.8 per cent).

Training evaluation is made properly in the organisation (68.4 per cent).It is found that the periodical organisational diagnosis is made in the organisation (69.5 per cent). The roles and authorities are well defined in the organisation (60.6 per cent) It is known that the HRD programmes implemented in the organisation is enhanced the quality of the employees (65.5 per cent). The career development opportunities are good in the organisation (61.9 per cent). It is found that the grievance handling method is good (65.8 per cent). There is a good relationship between the employees in the organization (69 per cent). Also the facilities provided in the organisation are good (65.2 per cent). The performance appraisal system has improved the organisational viability (82 per cent).It is found the restructuring is made after the diagnosis of the organisation (57 per cent).The employees records are maintained well in the organisation(54 per cent). The employees have a good self-discipline in the organisation (63 per cent).

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant association between the HRD programme of the organisation and the organisational efficiency.

Chi square test was applied

S. No.	HRD programmes	organizational Effectiveness		Statistical inference
		Low (n=190)	High (n=120)	
1	Low	95(50%)	28(23.3%)	X ² =21.852 Df=1 .000<0.05 Significant
2	High	95(50%)	92(76.7%)	

Table 03

The table no 03 shows that, the role of HRD programme in the overall organisational effectiveness. It has high level perception (76.7 per cent). Hence the calculated value is higher than the table value; HRD program has significant relationship in the organisational effectiveness.

SUGGESTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS

Based on the findings of the research, the researcher suggests the following interventions and steps to enhance the present level. A minimum numbers of the employees are not agreed with the current HRD programmes are not effective in nature; it reveals that they are the deviants or not actively take part in the organisational activities. It is suggested that the organization should identify and make

them to involve in the organisational activities regularly. The restructuring and the employees' record maintenance are comparatively low level opinion with other practices. It has to be improved.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

There are suggestions for further studies. This study can be extended to other manufacturing sectors to help them attain better HRD programmes and organisational effectiveness. In-depth studies can be done on each dimension of HRD programmes and organisational effectiveness. Study can be done to understand the HRD programmes and organisational effectiveness in different sectors and can be extended to educational institutions, hospitals, private and public sectors manufacturing industries.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Organisational effectiveness is the newly emerging field which is being practiced in almost all types of the organizations. It develops the relationship between the employees and the organization. An employee should know the all practices of that organization. Perhaps he can fully contribute his ability and talent for the development of the organization. The present study attempts to know the relationship between the HRD programmes and organisational effectiveness in the Tamil Nadu Newsprint Paper Limited, Karur, Tamil Nadu, India.

Organisational effectiveness is closely linked with the productivity of the organization. If the HRD program of the organisation are effective and timely adopted in nature, well defined, more familiar to the employees it helps to go in correct direction. Perhaps HRD programme plays a vital role in the organisational effectiveness.

APPENDIX

Opinion of the respondents on HRD practices

S. No.	Item	SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Mean
1	There is a well-defined policy in all and it is more familiar to the employees levels in my organisation	8 (2.6%)	9 (2.9%)	37 (11.9%)	200 (64.5%)	56 (18.1%)	3.93
2	My organisation has a healthy HRD programmes and it motivated me to do the job better	2 (0.6%)	3 (1%)	33 (10.6%)	204 (65.8%)	68 (21.9%)	4.18
3	If any change made in my organisation immediate and well equipped training will be given to the employees to adopt the change	3 (1%)	3 (1%)	11 (3.5%)	206 (66.5%)	87 (28.1%)	4.20
4	The training programme has improved my knowledge ,skills and potentiality	4 (1.3%)	2 (0.6%)	15 (4.8%)	201 (64.8%)	88(28.4%)	4.18
5	The training programme given in my organisation is well evaluated by the expert committees	8 (2.6%)	7 (2.3%)	19 (6.1%)	212 (68.4%)	64 (20.6%)	4.02

6	The periodical organisational diagnosis has done in my organisation	3 (1%)	3 (1%)	23 (7.4%)	214 (69%)	67 (21.6%)	4.09
7	The roles and authority in my organisation is well defined	2 (0.6%)	2 (0.6%)	18 (5.8%)	188 (60.6%)	100 (32.3%)	4.23
8	All the HRD programmes followed in my organisation are enhancing the quality of the employees	2 (0.6%)	5 (1.6%)	31 (10%)	202 (65.2%)	70 (22.6%)	4.07
9	My organisation provides a better career development opportunity	2 (0.6%)	11 (3.5%)	38 (12.3%)	192 (61.9%)	67 (21.6%)	4.00
10	I feel that I am a real asset of my organisation	2 (0.6%)	5 (1.6%)	2 (0.6%)	241 (77.7%)	60 (19.4%)	4.14
11	The grievance handling policy is good in my organization	2 (0.6%)	4 (1.3%)	29 (9.4%)	204 (65.8%)	71 (22.9%)	4.09
12	All employees in my organization have cordial relationship	2 (0.6%)	2 (0.6%)	15 (4.8%)	214 (69%)	77 (24.8%)	4.17
13	The facilities provided in my organisation is good	2 (0.6%)	1 (0.3%)	11 (3.5%)	202 (65.2%)	94 (30.3%)	4.24
14	Performance appraisal designed in my organisation is based on developing the organisation viability	2 (0.6%)	8 (2.6%)	33 (10.6%)	9 (2.9%)	258 (83.2%)	4.65
15	All the stakeholders of my organisation are well treated	2 (0.6%)	4 (1.3%)	10 (3.2%)	179 (57.7%)	115 (37.1%)	4.29
16	Restructuring the organisation done after the organisational diagnosis in my organisation	3 (1%)	2 (0.6%)	18 (5.8%)	179 (57.7%)	108 (34.8%)	4.25
17	The promotion opportunity given in my organization is good	3 (1%)	6 (1.9%)	22 (7.1%)	175 (56.5%)	104 (33.5%)	4.20
18	Good HRIS is maintained in my organisation	3 (1%)	4 (1.3%)	26 (8.4%)	168 (54.2%)	109 (35.2%)	4.21
19	Team work development practices are good in my organization	3 (1%)	2 (0.6%)	14 (4.5%)	206 (66.5%)	85 (27.4%)	4.19
20	Self-discipline within the organization is strictly maintained	3 (1%)	2 (0.6%)	24 (7.7%)	196 (63.2%)	85 (27.4%)	4.15

Source –primary data

Table -02

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Armstrong Michael, (1998). A Hand book on Human Resource Management. First Edison, T.R Publication P (Ltd)

Brenda S., Seevers, (2000). Organizational values and to investigate possible relationships, Journal of Agricultural Education , vol.41 Issue 3, pp70-79

Castle, Dian K.,& Michael (2001). Organizational understanding and change management that enables a successful implementation of IT projects. Teaching and learning Resource- 21st century: A Reference Hand book, Edited by Charles Wankel

Cummings., T Worley C, (2001). Organization development and change. South Western College Publishing

Cummings, T (2004). Organization development and change, Foundations and applications- In Dynamics of Organizational Change and Learning. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.

French, W (1969). Organizational Development Objectives, assumptions, and Stretgies. 13(2), 23-24

Gupta, S.P (1991). Statistical Methods. Twenty sixth Edison, Sultan Chand & Sons Publishers: New Delhi.

Harry Sminia & Antonie Van Nistelrooij (2006). Introduction of organization development (OD) techniques in a traditionally top-down lead public sector organization in the Netherlands

Jacob, D (2010). Organizational development practices in ONGC: Cauvery Assets, Karaikkal, An unpublished research work, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli.

Kothari, C.R (1997). Research Methodology (methods and techniques) Second Edison Wishwa Prakashan: New Delhi

Marc Bonnet & Michel Peron (2008). Approaches to Organization Development: Organization Development Journal

Richard K., Ladyshefsky (2010). Organizational development. Leadership and Organization Development Journal: Emerald Group Publishing Ltd Vol 31 No 4, pp 292-306

Subramaniyan K., (2011). Organisation climate in TNPL, Karur. An unpublished research work, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli.

Web sites:

<http://www.csrromania>
<http://www.emeraldinsight.comresearcherregister>
<http://www.managementjournals.com>
<http://www.tandf.co.uk/journals>
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